

The Geometry of Interference: Quantifying Spatial Leakage and Biomechanical Adaptation During Human–Robot Collaboration

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Abstract—While industrial safety standards for Human-Robot Collaboration (HRC) prioritize collision avoidance through static distance metrics, they provide limited means to quantify the continuous motor interference imposed on human operators. This study introduces Distractor-Aligned Variance (DAV), a continuous measurement framework designed to characterize how active robotic interference structurally reshapes human motor execution. We analyzed human kinematics ($N = 48$) in a synchronized pick-and-place task, systematically manipulating trajectory profiles (Rectilinear vs. Curvilinear), spatial layouts, and hardware mounting configurations. To mitigate the sensitivity of static orthogonal metrics to curvature effects, we employ a dynamic 3D-to-2D planar projection that separates variance aligned with the task direction from orthogonal spatial variability. Our results demonstrate that geometric disparity, quantified as the angular incongruency between human and robot velocity vectors, is consistently associated with spatial leakage, particularly under piecewise rectilinear trajectories. Furthermore, we identify covariation between these geometric patterns and behavioral markers of biomechanical adaptation, specifically arm joint freezing and reduced kinematic smoothness. These findings suggest that trajectory-based interference is a multi-dimensional phenomenon where geometric conflict is linked to motor adaptation patterns. This framework provides metrics that may inform human-aware trajectory planning in shared workspaces, supporting the design of robotic systems that account for the kinematic structure of human movement.

Index Terms—Human-Robot Collaboration, Motor Interference, Spatial Leakage, Kinematic Variability, Human-Aware Robotics, Proxemics.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE integration of collaborative robots (cobots) into shared industrial workspaces fundamentally alters the spatial dynamics of human labor [1]. Prevailing international safety standards [2], [3] and technical specifications [4] rely heavily on static, distance-based separation to ensure operator safety. While these geometric constraints successfully mitigate the risk of physical collision [5], they treat the human operator as a static obstacle rather than a dynamic, predictive agent. As a result, modern trajectory planners often prioritize absolute machine efficiency by minimizing path length and execution time, inadvertently imposing measurable cognitive and kinematic penalties on the human partner [6]. Although recent human-aware planning approaches have incorporated concepts such as legibility and predictability, comparatively

little attention has been given to continuously quantifying how active robot motion physically alters the spatial structure of human motor execution.

A key determinant of continuous physical interaction quality is *Motor Interference* (MI), a disturbance in motor execution triggered by the observation of, or synchronization with, an incongruent movement [7], [8]. In HRC, human spatial negotiation depends on a complex interplay of variables. The interpretation of a robot’s motion is intrinsically shaped not only by its dynamic path but also by perceived workspace occupancy [9]. To date, HRI literature has frequently compartmentalized these factors, studying hardware proxemics [11], trajectory legibility [12], and motor interference [13] in isolation.

To bridge this gap, previous work evaluating this experimental paradigm has established the macroscopic spatial boundaries and psychological workload penalties dictated by hardware embodiment and spatial conflict [24], including absolute proxemic clearance, maximum spatial envelope expansion, temporal synchronization, and NASA-TLX workload. Building upon that foundation, this study proposes a continuous framework that evaluates the underlying human spatial negotiation by isolating two primary dynamic dimensions of interaction: *distractor-aligned variance* and *biomechanical adaptation*. This structure is inspired by computational models of sensorimotor control, which conceptualize movement as a layered sequence involving the perception of environmental constraints, the planning of motor actions, and biomechanical execution with continuous feedback correction [14], [15]. By evaluating HRC through this established biological sequence, we can trace how a robot’s active kinematics alter human performance. We hypothesized that when a human operator encounters an incongruent cobot motion, the resulting disturbance would manifest not merely as increased general movement variability, but as a structural variance expansion aligned with the distractor axis, accompanied by a measurable biomechanical adaptation. The present work does not re-evaluate subjective workload, proxemic boundaries, or behavioral performance outcomes. Instead, it investigates the continuous kinematic organization that may accompany those previously reported effects.

We conducted a controlled, within-subjects experiment ($N = 48$) utilizing a continuous, synchronized pick-and-place task to evaluate the interactions between coupled trajectory profiles (Rectilinear vs. Curvilinear) and the physical spatial mode (opposite-side vs. same-side), while manipulating hard-

This work was supported by the German Research Foundation (DFG) under Grant nos. KU 2486/8-1, KU 2486/8-2 and KU 2486/9-1.

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ware mounting (table vs. shoulder) to control for baseline workspace occupancy.

This work is not intended as a new foundational theory of motor control, nor does it present a standalone planning algorithm. Rather, it introduces a diagnostic measurement tool. By operationalizing spatial conflict, the primary contributions of this paper align with this sensorimotor sequence:

- 1) **Controlled Baseline (Hardware Occupancy):** We demonstrate that, within the tested configurations, static hardware mounting acts as a minor contextual constraint. While table-mounted setups slightly expand the baseline spatial footprint ($\eta_p^2 = 0.01$), they do not compound dynamic interference, isolating active geometric conflict as the dominant predictor of motor deviation.
- 2) **Geometric Motor Deviation (The Primary Variance Expansion):** We introduce a dynamic 3D-to-2D planar projection framework to quantify distractor-aligned variance, conceptually referred to as *spatial leakage*. This approach analytically mitigates first-order curvature-induced pacing artifacts while explicitly preserving critical sagittal avoidance behaviors. Using this framework, we demonstrate that the continuous geometric disparity between human and robot velocity vectors emerges as a strong geometric predictor of the observed variance expansion, corresponding to a pronounced variance expansion along the incongruent distractor axis (V_{v_i}).
- 3) **Execution (Biomechanical Adaptation):** We connect the observed geometric spatial leakage to underlying behavioral markers of motor control effort. Our analysis confirms that this trajectory-based interference exhibits a reliable association with kinematic stiffening, specifically corresponding to increased arm joint freezing and elevated kinematic jerk.

II. RELATED WORK AND METHODOLOGICAL CONTRIBUTION

To establish the utility of this dynamic projection framework, it is necessary to contextualize it within existing frameworks for evaluating human motor variability and spatial interference.

A. Traditional Metrics of Motor Interference

Early investigations into MI primarily relied on discrete, macroscopic metrics. Studies evaluating human-human and human-robot synchronization often quantify interference as an increase in total reaction time, completion time, or final endpoint variance [7]. While effective for establishing the presence of cognitive load or task degradation, these endpoint metrics aggregate the entire movement into a single summary statistic, masking the continuous structural breakdown of the trajectory.

When continuous tracking is employed, classic MI literature typically quantifies interference as the maximum absolute deviation orthogonal to a straight-line path [8], [13]. However, this assumes a static Cartesian coordinate system and linear reference movements. In modern HRC, cobots execute continuous curvilinear trajectories (e.g., minimum-jerk

curves). Evaluating non-linear spatial negotiation using static orthogonal metrics becomes susceptible to curvature-induced pacing artifacts, conflating a human’s temporal yielding with true structural spatial deviation.

B. Task-Space Covariance and Redundancy

Within the computational motor control literature, movement variability is frequently analyzed through the lens of redundancy and task-space covariance. Frameworks such as the Uncontrolled Manifold (UCM) theory [16] and optimal feedback control [17] decompose variance into task-relevant dimensions (variance that degrades performance) and task-irrelevant dimensions (variance that exploits biomechanical redundancy without affecting the goal).

While the underlying algebra of our proposed approach utilizes similar covariance eigendecomposition, our theoretical objective and level of analysis fundamentally differ from UCM. Traditional UCM projects high-dimensional *joint-space* variance onto a lower-dimensional *task-space* manifold to study internal motor synergies. In contrast, our framework operates entirely within the external operational task space, projecting 3D Cartesian tracking data onto localized dynamic planes to quantify spatial negotiation with a moving robotic distractor.

C. Contribution: A Continuous Measurement Framework

The primary methodological contribution of this paper is not the algebraic decomposition of variance itself, but rather the formulation of a dynamic, frame-by-frame 3D-to-2D planar projection of task-space variance that explicitly preserves critical 3D avoidance behaviors.

Existing global covariance-based analyses typically characterize the overall shape of a movement trajectory post hoc. The proposed framework instead introduces a localized, dynamic formulation. By mapping the instantaneous 3D covariance matrix $\Sigma(t)$ onto distinct 2D projection planes governed by the intended path ($\hat{v}_c(t)$) and the competing distractor path ($\hat{v}_i(t)$), while sharing the orthogonal sagittal depth axis (\hat{x}), this approach successfully decouples longitudinal pacing errors from true distractor-aligned variance (spatial leakage) without discarding real-world depth kinematics.

Unlike static orthogonal MI metrics, this dynamic planar formulation exhibits first-order invariance to curvature-induced pacing artifacts and accommodates the changing angle of incidence inherent to curvilinear cobot trajectories. Therefore, it provides trajectory planners with a continuous evaluation metric to quantify exactly *when* and *where* the geometric disparity of a robot’s non-linear motion profile corresponds to an expansion of the human operator’s spatial variance into the shared workspace. This framework offers a common geometric language through which biological motor variability can inform robotic trajectory evaluation and continuous spatial interference modeling.

III. EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

A. Participants and Experimental Design

The study utilized a fully within-subjects repeated measures design. To provide immediate clarity on the intersecting

experimental manipulations, Table I defines the independent variables governing the interaction.

TABLE I: Definition of Independent Experimental Variables

Variable (Levels)	Meaning
Spatial Mode (<i>Same-side / Opposite-side</i>)	Static workspace layout and human-robot proximity
Direction (<i>Congruent / Incongruent</i>)	Instantaneous task-oriented motion relationship
Trajectory (<i>Curvilinear / Rectilinear</i>)	Dynamic shape of the robot's kinematic profile
Mounting (<i>Shoulder / Table</i>)	Physical hardware embodiment and workspace occupancy

A cohort of forty-eight participants ($N = 48$; $M_{\text{age}} = 24.2$, $SD = 5.8$ years; 50% female, 50% male, 87.5% right-handed) completed the study. To ensure no systematic biomechanical bias across conditions due to varying anthropometry, participants were seated in a standardized, height-adjustable chair and calibrated their distance to the shared task interface to ensure consistent and comfortable reaching kinematics. Participants were recruited from the university population and reported no professional experience operating industrial robots. All participants were screened to ensure no developmental or movement disabilities, and all performed the task using their right arm to standardize the kinematic data. The experimental protocol was approved by the University Ethics Committee, and all participants provided written informed consent prior to the experiment.

Fig. 1: Wide view of the experimental setup. The workspace features the UR3 collaborative robot arm, the OptiTrack Trio optical tracking system, and the participant seated at the shared task interface. The global spatial origin for all coordinate mapping is anchored to the robot's initial end-effector position.

The experiment was conducted using a UR3 collaborative robot arm (Universal Robots®, Denmark) in a shared workspace, as shown in Fig. 1. To evaluate the effect of physical workspace occupancy on baseline kinematics, the experiment was conducted under two distinct mounting configurations:

Table-mounted (the robot base was affixed to the shared workspace table, imposing physical and visual occlusion) and *Shoulder-mounted* (the robot was mounted above and behind the workspace).

Within each configuration, participants encountered the fully crossed dynamic conditions. During the *Same-side* spatial mode, the human and robot operated in parallel workspace zones, sharing the intended motion plane. During the *Opposite-side* mode, they operated in converging workspace zones. Within each physical mode, each cyclic movement contained a *Congruent* direction (human and robot moving toward the same target side) and an *Incongruent* direction (moving toward opposite targets, maximizing geometric crossing conflict). Finally, the robot's motion was manipulated between a continuous *Curvilinear* profile and a piecewise *Rectilinear* profile.

Participants executed $K = 15$ reciprocal pick-and-place repetitions per condition in synchrony with the deterministic motion of the robot. To strictly control for neuromuscular fatigue and motor-learning artifacts across these repeated measures, all dynamic trajectory conditions were presented using balanced Latin-square sequences. This repetition count was selected to provide robust covariance estimation while maintaining participant comfort.

B. Hardware Mounting Configurations

To evaluate the baseline context of static hardware, the robot was physically reconfigured between two mounting states. In the *Table-mounted* configuration, the robot's base was affixed directly to the shared planar workspace, altering approach vectors and visual occlusion. In the *Shoulder-mounted* configuration, the robot was elevated on an aluminum frame, aligning the base approximately at the lateral elevation of a human operator's arm (without replicating humanoid morphology), altering workspace occupancy compared to the table-mounted setup.

C. Coupled Trajectory Profiling and Generation

Trajectory generation followed the experimentally validated framework detailed in our parallel evaluation of macroscopic spatial boundaries [24], and is summarized here strictly to establish the kinematic conditions relevant to the present continuous variance analyses.

To isolate the geometric shape of the trajectory from temporal confounds, both *Curvilinear* and *Rectilinear* robotic profiles (visualized in Fig. 2) were constrained to an identical cycle time. The transport segments executed in exactly 2.0s, reaching a shared intermediate via-point at $t = 1.0$ s. To enforce a highly controlled spatial conflict without conflating execution time, the robot's motion was governed by a strict mathematical dichotomy:

- **Curvilinear Profile (Continuous Momentum):** Operating as the baseline, this motion was generated as a single, continuous minimum-jerk trajectory [18], allowing continuous momentum to carry the end-effector through the waypoint with lower peak accelerations.

Fig. 2: Comprehensive spatial footprint of the $2 \times 2 \times 2$ experimental conditions. The columns contrast the static *Shoulder-mounted* and *Table-mounted* hardware configurations. The rows contrast the *Rectilinear* and *Curvilinear* trajectory kinematics. Overlaid are the deterministic robot reference paths (green) and the resulting human trajectories (yellow) for both congruent (same-side) and incongruent (opposite-side) task directions.

- Rectilinear Profile (Piecewise Translation):** The motion was divided into two independent minimum-jerk segments. By applying zero-velocity and zero-acceleration constraints at the intermediate via-point, the robot executed a direct linear translation, came to a complete stop, rotated its velocity vector, and executed a secondary linear translation.

Because this Rectilinear profile forces the robot to traverse a longer orthogonal path within the exact same temporal duration as the Curvilinear profile (2.0s), it inherently demands substantially higher peak kinematics to satisfy the temporal boundary constraints. Specifically, the Rectilinear motion requires a peak velocity of 0.56 m/s and peak acceleration of 1.73 m/s^2 , compared to the Curvilinear baseline (0.47 m/s and 1.41 m/s^2). This zero-velocity constraint was deliberately selected to isolate the effect of discrete, orthogonal kinematic state transitions from the continuously varying momentum of the Curvilinear profile, representing the distinctly more aggressive physical stimulus required to evaluate geometric spatial leakage.

D. Data Acquisition and Coordinate Mapping

Three-dimensional human limb and robot end-effector kinematics were recorded at 120 Hz using an OptiTrack Trio[®] optical tracking system and processed via a custom MATLAB pipeline. Missing marker data were minimal (accounting for $< 1\%$ of total recorded frames) and were reconstructed using linear interpolation with nearest-neighbor edge padding.

All human trajectories were retained in absolute chronological time rather than being temporally normalized; the explicit frame-by-frame alignment strategy utilized for dynamic spatial projection is detailed in Section III-F.

To ensure accurate geometric modeling of the spatial interference, the global coordinate origin was anchored to the robot's initial end-effector position rather than a human-centered frame. Because the robot generates the deterministic trajectories constituting the experimental motion stimulus, a robot-centered frame provides a stationary, immutable reference. Utilizing a human-centered frame (e.g., a sternum-anchored origin) would introduce confounding variability from natural postural sway and torso translation, which would artificially inflate the measurement of the arm's trajectory variance. The task space was mapped such that the $+x$ -axis represents the frontal depth vector (sagittal axis) originating from the robot and pointing toward the human participant. The y -axis represents the lateral vector, and the z -axis represents the vertical vector (creating the primary yz motion plane).

Raw kinematic trajectories were smoothed using a second-order, zero-phase Butterworth low-pass filter (6 Hz cutoff), consistent with established practice in human movement biomechanics [19]. Filtering was performed prior to the computation of derivative-based quantities because velocity, acceleration, and jerk are particularly sensitive to high-frequency measurement noise. This standardized, robot-anchored coordinate system provides the necessary 3D geometric foundation for the dynamic planar projections, the mathematical invariance of which is formally derived in Section IV-G.

E. Quantifying Geometric Conflict (Directional Incongruency)

To explicitly quantify the instantaneous geometric conflict driving spatial negotiation, we define a continuous *Directional Incongruency* ratio ($\text{Inc}(t)$). While categorical task variables (e.g., Spatial Mode) define the macroscopic environment, $\text{Inc}(t)$ serves as a continuous metric representing the real-time angular disparity between the human operator and the robot.

Let $\hat{\mathbf{v}}_h(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ and $\hat{\mathbf{v}}_r(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ denote the unit-normalized, instantaneous velocity vectors of the human hand and the robot end-effector, respectively. The directional incongruency at any time step t is formulated as:

$$\text{Inc}(t) = 1 - |\hat{\mathbf{v}}_h(t) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{v}}_r(t)| \quad (1)$$

This formulation yields a bounded scalar metric ranging from 0 to 1. The absolute dot product ensures that both perfectly parallel and perfectly anti-parallel movements evaluate to 0 because their velocity vectors are strictly collinear. In this framework, collinearity, regardless of sign, is treated as geometrically congruent because interference is hypothesized to arise from directional crossing rather than opposition

along a common axis. Conversely, as the angle of incidence approaches 90° (a perfectly orthogonal crossing), the dot product approaches 0, and $\text{Inc}(t)$ peaks at 1. By utilizing unit vectors, this metric isolates pure geometric disparity, remaining completely independent of the scalar speed of either agent.

This metric intentionally isolates geometric crossing conflict rather than directional agreement. Therefore, anti-parallel trajectories receive the same score as parallel trajectories because both configurations are collinear and do not introduce orthogonal spatial competition.

For statistical evaluation, $\text{Inc}(t)$ is utilized in two capacities: as a continuous time-series predictor to evaluate instantaneous covariation with human kinematics, and temporally aggregated via the maximum operator ($\text{Inc}^* = \max_t(\text{Inc}(t))$) to represent the maximum directional incongruency observed during a trial. This establishes the formal independent variable required to evaluate the subsequent structural deformation of the observed movement distribution.

F. Quantifying Spatial Leakage (Kinematic Planar Formulation)

To move beyond macroscopic endpoint variance, we evaluated the continuous deviation of the human’s movement variability mid-trajectory. Mathematically, we quantify this via **Distractor-Aligned Variance (DAV)**: a specific geometric quantity representing the magnitude of human kinematic variance mapped onto a dynamic 2D projection plane governed by a competing, incongruent trajectory. Throughout this paper, the term *spatial leakage* refers to the behavioral manifestation of elevated DAV.

Let $K = 15$ denote the number of repeated trials per condition. Rather than relying on subjective kinematic cutoffs (e.g., a 5% peak velocity threshold) which artificially mask reaction-time delays, movement onset ($t = 0$) was deterministically defined by the robot’s hardware state machine. The continuous optical tracking data was systematically bounded to the precise timestamps marking the initiation and termination of the robot’s transport phase, ensuring human synchronization delays and pacing adaptations remained captured within the chronological variance structure. These temporally aligned trajectories were mapped across discrete 120 Hz time frames. Let \mathcal{O}_t denote the subset of valid, unpadded trial observations available at frame t , and let $K_t = |\mathcal{O}_t|$ represent the count of these active trials. The spatial distribution of the hand at any given moment is characterized by its 3×3 sample covariance matrix:

$$\Sigma(t) = \frac{1}{K_t - 1} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{O}_t} (\mathbf{x}_k(t) - \bar{\mathbf{x}}(t))(\mathbf{x}_k(t) - \bar{\mathbf{x}}(t))^\top \quad (2)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{x}}(t)$ is the mean spatial position of the active trials at time step t . When trailing observations were unavailable due to individual pacing adaptations, covariance estimates were computed strictly from the subset of valid observations present at that frame. Frames containing fewer than two valid observations ($K_t < 2$) were excluded from covariance estimation to prevent undefined mathematical divisions.

This covariance is computed *across* repeated executions at each time step, rather than along the temporal axis of a single trajectory. In computational motor control, trial-to-trial variability is widely used to characterize the consistency and stability of motor execution under sensorimotor noise and environmental perturbations [20], [17], [21]. Because the present framework seeks to quantify how reliably participants reproduce a spatial strategy while interacting with a moving robot, covariance across repeated executions provides a principled measure of execution consistency under varying interference conditions.

Increased spatial covariance is therefore interpreted as a behavioral signature of reduced movement consistency, which aligns with elevated motor-control demands under interference, rather than merely as a geometric deviation from an ideal path. The use of repeated synchronized movements aligns with prior human-robot coordination studies demonstrating systematic evolution of trajectory variability across repeated interactions [22], [23].

The conceptual basis of this framework is illustrated in Fig. 3, where the 3D kinematic data cloud (Fig. 3a) is dynamically mapped onto 2D projection planes (Fig. 3b). Rather than collapsing 3D data into static Cartesian scalar distances, the covariance structure is projected onto planes that continuously co-rotate with the task-relevant velocity vectors while preserving the sagittal depth axis.

Because spatial interference introduces competing kinematic attractors, we dynamically evaluate the eigendecomposition of the 3D covariance matrix:

$$\Sigma(t) = \mathbf{U}(t)\Lambda(t)\mathbf{U}^\top(t) \quad (3)$$

The eigendecomposition serves as a diagnostic characterization of covariance anisotropy and provides the mathematical basis for the confidence ellipsoids used for visualization.

Because a curvilinear trajectory involves a changing angle of incidence, motor interference does not manifest as a fixed geometric leak, but rather as a directional variance expansion relative to the distractor trajectory. To capture this without discarding real-world depth kinematics, the spatial variance is mapped onto dynamic 2D basis matrices.

Let $\hat{\mathbf{v}}_c(t)$ and $\hat{\mathbf{v}}_i(t)$ represent the instantaneous, unit-normalized planar velocity vectors of the congruent (intended) robot path and the incongruent (distractor) robot path, respectively. Let $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ represent the static, orthogonal unit vector of the sagittal depth axis. The Intended Motion Plane and the Distractor Motion Plane are spanned by the 3×2 basis matrices $P_c(t)$ and $P_i(t)$:

$$P_c(t) = [\hat{\mathbf{v}}_c(t), \hat{\mathbf{x}}], \quad P_i(t) = [\hat{\mathbf{v}}_i(t), \hat{\mathbf{x}}] \quad (4)$$

The 3D covariance is projected onto these planes to generate instantaneous 2×2 planar covariance matrices (Σ_{P_c} and Σ_{P_i}). To extract a comparable scalar variance magnitude from these planes, we calculate the Trace (Tr) of the projected matrices:

$$V_{\mathbf{v}_c}(t) = \text{Tr}(P_c(t)^\top \Sigma(t) P_c(t)) \quad (5)$$

$$V_{\mathbf{v}_i}(t) = \text{Tr}(P_i(t)^\top \Sigma(t) P_i(t)) \quad (6)$$

(a) 3D spatial variance at a single aligned time frame.

(b) 2D kinematic planar projection isolating spatial leakage.

Fig. 3: Geometric derivation of spatial leakage. The 3D kinematic data cloud (a) is mapped onto dynamic 2D projection planes (b). The coordinate system dictates that the $+x$ -axis originates from the robot and points toward the human (sagittal depth). Rather than reducing variance to static scalar lines, the variance is projected onto dynamic 2D planes: the Intended Motion Plane (V_{v_c}) and the Distractor Motion Plane (V_{v_i}), both of which share the x -axis to preserve sagittal avoidance behaviors.

The trace (Tr) mathematically sums the variance along the projection plane’s respective velocity vector and the orthogonal sagittal depth axis (\hat{x}). This metric was deliberately selected over alternatives such as the determinant or the isolated maximum eigenvalue. While the determinant (representing ellipse area) mathematically collapses if variance is tightly restricted along a single axis, the trace captures the total magnitude of spatial negotiation within the plane. This is critical in 3D human-robot crossings, as operators may evade interference either by deviating laterally or by retreating in depth.

This formulation represents a fundamental departure from traditional moving-frame Principal Component Analysis (PCA). While PCA dynamically aligns its axes to maximize data variance (a purely data-driven description of noise), the proposed projection maps variance onto predetermined spatial attractors dictated by the robot’s kinematics (a hypothesis-driven approach). This ensures that V_{v_i} quantifies the variance specifically drawn into the distractor-aligned projection plane, rather than merely identifying the principal axis of general execution noise.

This yields two targeted, continuous parameters:

- $V_{v_c}(t)$: The total variance upon the Intended Motion Plane. Because it maps strictly onto the congruent velocity vector, this longitudinal channel is expected to contain pacing-related variability and temporal execution noise.
- $V_{v_i}(t)$: The Distractor-Aligned Variance (DAV). Because this plane is spanned by the incongruent velocity vector and the sagittal depth axis (\hat{x}), DAV does not exclusively isolate the distractor vector; rather, it quantifies the total variance within the distractor-aligned projection plane.

Spatial leakage, as the behavioral interpretation of DAV, does not directly measure signed physical displacement toward the distractor path. Instead, increased variance across this specific projection plane (V_{v_i}) mathematically reflects a reduced ability of the human operator to maintain strict 3D kinematic confinement to the intended trajectory under the incongruent movement direction.

To generate the scalar metrics required for the Linear Mixed-Effects Models (LMMs), these continuous instantaneous planar variances are temporally aggregated by extracting the absolute maximum spatial variance across the time series:

$$V_{v_c}^* = \max_t (V_{v_c}(t)), \quad V_{v_i}^* = \max_t (V_{v_i}(t)) \quad (7)$$

Because spatial negotiation during the crossing phase is expected to be temporally localized within the trajectory, extracting a single representative value for the interaction relies on the peak interference magnitude rather than the temporal mean. Aggregation methods such as the temporal mean or integral were rejected, as they mathematically dilute this localized geometric deviation with the baseline variance of the unaffected transport and deceleration phases. To empirically verify that this peak extraction is not artificially inflated by residual tracking artifacts, a robustness check utilizing the 95th percentile (P_{95}) of the temporal variance was conducted. This produced statistically equivalent conclusions (e.g., preserving the critical Direction \times Trajectory interaction, $p = 0.031$; see

Appendix A for full model outputs), confirming the stability of the dynamic planar framework. This formulation accommodates the changing angle of curvilinear interference while preserving critical depth geometry, isolating spatial disruption and capturing the peak geometric deviation of the observed movement distribution.

G. Biomechanical Adaptation Metrics

To verify that the geometric variance observed via this dynamic projection framework corresponds to an increase in motor control demands, we analyzed underlying markers of biomechanical adaptation:

- **Arm Joint Freeze:** Quantified via the continuous Distal-Proximal Velocity Ratio (the magnitude of distal wrist translation divided by the magnitude of proximal shoulder translation) during the transport phase. A proportional reduction in this ratio signifies the suppression of distal degrees of freedom and an increased reliance on rigid torso/shoulder compensation. Lower values indicate reduced distal contribution, representing kinematic stiffening in response to spatial interference.
- **Kinematic Jerk Score:** Evaluated using a Logarithmic Dimensionless Jerk (LDJ) metric. The time-derivative of acceleration is squared and integrated over the movement path, normalized by the cube of the movement duration and the square of the peak velocity, and subsequently log-transformed. This dimensionless scaling is widely used to quantify the loss of motor smoothness and the presence of sub-movements (corrective effort), substantially reducing mathematical dependence on movement duration, speed, and path length.

IV. RESULTS

A. Statistical Analysis and Model Specification

To account for inter-individual variability and the repeated-measures structure of the data, all statistical inferences were conducted using Linear Mixed-Effects Models (LMMs) fit via Restricted Maximum Likelihood (REML). For each kinematic and biomechanical metric, the fixed-effects structure included the fully crossed interaction of the primary dynamic experimental manipulations.

In Wilkinson notation, the baseline theoretical model was specified as:

$$Y \sim \text{Direction} * \text{Trajectory} * \text{Spatial_Mode} + (1 \mid \text{Participant}) \quad (8)$$

(For the evaluation of static hardware occupancy, the *Mount* configuration was additionally included as a fixed effect).

Following established guidelines for mixed-effects modeling, we initially specified maximal random-effects structures incorporating random slopes for all within-subject fixed factors. However, due to the high consistency of within-subject variance, this maximal specification resulted in model singularity and convergence failures driven by overparameterization. To achieve convergence without overfitting, the random-effects structure was iteratively simplified via a principled step-down procedure. The final parsimonious models were specified with

random intercepts for each participant (1 | Participant). This structure successfully resolved singularity issues while rigorously accounting for baseline inter-individual differences.

Prior to omnibus testing, the assumptions of the LMMs were evaluated. Normality of the residuals was confirmed via visual inspection of quantile-quantile (Q-Q) plots, and homoscedasticity was verified by examining scatter plots of the fitted values against the residuals.

P -values for the fixed effects were estimated using Satterthwaite’s approximation for denominator degrees of freedom to account for unbalancedness. To evaluate the practical significance of the findings, we report estimated marginal means (M) and 95% Confidence Intervals (CI). For continuous regression models, both marginal and conditional R^2 values are reported to quantify variance explained by the fixed effects alone and by the full mixed-effects model. Additionally, pseudo-partial effect sizes (η_p^2) were computed from the F -statistics and Satterthwaite-approximated degrees of freedom utilizing the `effectsize` package to maintain direct comparability with the classical behavioral motor control literature (all subsequent reported η_p^2 values throughout this manuscript refer to these pseudo-partial estimates).

B. Validation of Planar Confinement

Before examining the dynamic projection within the motion plane, we evaluated the geometric boundaries of the spatial interference by analyzing out-of-plane sagittal depth shifts (*ProjX*). The LMM revealed a significant main effect, where the *Incongruent* direction corresponded to a larger absolute shift out of the primary movement plane ($F(1, 713) = 29.31$, $p < 0.001$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.04$). However, there was no significant difference between the *Same-side* and *Opposite-side* spatial modes for this out-of-plane projection ($F(1, 713) = 0.00$, $p = 1.000$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.00$), nor were there any significant interactions. These findings suggest that the dominant variance effects occurred within the primary motion plane (yz -plane) rather than through systematic sagittal-depth deviations, supporting the focus of the subsequent dynamic projection framework.

C. Baseline Context: The Hardware Mounting Effect

We investigated how the static hardware configuration influenced the footprint of the human’s intended motion. Analysis of the overall area of the intended path variance (the 2D area bounding V_{vc}) revealed a significant main effect for the *Robot Mount* ($F(1, 705) = 7.24$, $p = 0.007$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.01$). The *Table-mounted* configuration ($M = 28633.26$, 95% CI [25937.10, 31329.41]) was associated with a modest increase in the baseline area of the congruent variance compared to the *Shoulder-mounted* setup ($M = 27003.54$, 95% CI [24307.38, 29699.69]). This finding establishes that, before dynamic trajectory factors are considered, an industrial table-mounted configuration corresponds to a consistent, albeit minor, expansion of the human operator’s spatial footprint for the intended path. A comprehensive evaluation of how this specific hardware embodiment alters absolute 3D Euclidean safety margins and subjective psychological disturbance (NASA-TLX) is detailed in [24], allowing the present analysis to focus strictly on the continuous, mid-trajectory motor deviations.

D. Primary Dynamic Effect: The Kinematic Variance Interaction

While the static hardware configuration established a minor baseline expansion of the intended path, it did not yield significant interactions with the dynamic variables. Focusing instead on the dynamic interaction within the yz motion plane, analysis revealed significant structural deviations in human motor execution. Both the *Incongruent* movement direction ($F(1, 713) = 805.62, p < 0.001, \eta_p^2 = 0.53$; Incongruent $M = 172.08 \text{ mm}^2, 95\% \text{ CI } [163.70, 180.46]$; Congruent $M = 68.46 \text{ mm}^2, 95\% \text{ CI } [62.96, 73.95]$) and the *Same-side* spatial mode ($F(1, 713) = 130.32, p < 0.001, \eta_p^2 = 0.15$; Same-side $M = 156.33 \text{ mm}^2, 95\% \text{ CI } [149.89, 162.77]$; Opposite-side $M = 120.27 \text{ mm}^2, 95\% \text{ CI } [113.06, 127.48]$) exhibited greater variance overall, manifested as a systematic elongation of the confidence ellipses along the distractor axis (see Fig. 4; full estimated marginal means and Tukey-adjusted post-hoc comparisons for all nested interactions are provided in Appendix B).

The significant $\text{Direction} \times \text{Trajectory}$ interaction ($F(1, 713) = 7.93, p = 0.005, \eta_p^2 = 0.01$) indicates that increases in variance were not uniformly distributed across the projected task space. Instead, the coupled *Rectilinear* profile was associated with a larger relative increase in Distractor-Aligned Variance (V_{v_i}) than in intended path variance (V_{v_c}). This directionally specific variance expansion evolves continuously throughout the interaction, peaking dynamically as the human and robot negotiate the shared workspace (see Fig. 5).

Fig. 4: Visual representation of the 95% confidence ellipses for spatial variance. The orientation and elongation of the confidence ellipses visualize the dominant directions of spatial variability. Under incongruent conditions, the covariance structure becomes increasingly aligned with the distractor axis, corresponding to larger values of Distractor-Aligned Variance (V_{v_i}), particularly when the robot executes abrupt Rectilinear movements.

(a) Time Evolution of Directional Incongruency

(b) Time Evolution of Spatial Leakage

Fig. 5: Dynamic temporal evolution of interaction metrics. For visualization purposes only, trajectories were rescaled to normalized movement time (0–100%), whereas all statistical analyses were performed strictly on the original absolute chronologically aligned data. (a) Directional incongruency captures the continuous geometric conflict between the human and robot paths. (b) Spatial variance demonstrates that Distractor-Aligned Variance (V_{v_i}) and intended path variance (V_{v_c}) both peak dynamically during interaction, with the incongruent mode coinciding with sustained elevated variance. Solid lines represent the mean, while shaded regions denote the 95% confidence bands (Standard Error).

This Distractor-Aligned Variance acts as an interactive variable when combined with the physical task layout. A significant three-way interaction ($\text{Direction} \times \text{Trajectory} \times \text{Spatial Mode}$, $F(1, 713) = 5.96, p = 0.015, \eta_p^2 = 0.01$) indicated that the compounding effect of the *Rectilinear* profile on this distractor-oriented deviation was most pronounced during the *Same-side* spatial mode (see Fig. 6). Similar interaction patterns were observed for the longitudinal variance (V_{v_c} , $F(1, 713) = 7.16, p = 0.008, \eta_p^2 = 0.01$). The same experimental conditions that were associated with increased distractor-aligned variance were also associated with increased intended-path variance. Both V_{v_i} and V_{v_c} are complementary projections derived from the same instantaneous 3D covariance matrix ($\Sigma(t)$). They do not represent strictly independent behavioral constructs, but rather orthogonal geometric dimensions of the overall variance expansion. As visualized

by the orientation of the confidence ellipses in Fig. 4, the variance expansion is highly anisotropic. Under incongruent interference, the primary eigenvectors of the covariance matrix systematically elongate and rotate to align with the distractor axis. This confirms that the observed variance is not merely a global inflation of execution noise, but a structural deformation directionally biased by the geometric conflict.

Fig. 6: Three-way interaction illustrating the compounding effect of Rectilinear robot kinematics on human spatial leakage. Estimated Marginal Means (EMMs) demonstrate that the abrupt Rectilinear profile exacerbates distractor-aligned variance most severely when the robot occupies the same intended motion plane as the human (Same-side spatial mode) during incongruent directional conflict, whereas it has a negligible compounding effect when occupying the opposite distractor plane.

E. Continuous Geometric Disparity as a Predictor of Spatial Leakage

To examine whether the geometric relationship between human and robot motion is associated with variations in spatial leakage, we fit a continuous linear mixed-effects model using the Directional Incongruity ratio as a predictor of Distractor-Aligned Variance (DAV). This metric reflects the angular alignment between human and robot velocity vectors and can be interpreted as a continuous proxy for directional mismatch (conceptually related to $|\hat{v}_h \cdot \hat{v}_r|$).

The model revealed a significant positive association between directional incongruity and DAV ($\beta = 190.33$, $t(745) = 27.65$, $p < 0.001$), as illustrated in Fig. 7. Given that the predictor is bounded in $[0, 1]$, the unstandardized coefficient is expressed in the original DAV scale (mm^2), which contributes to its large numerical magnitude without affecting interpretability.

Overall, the fixed effect of directional incongruity accounted for a substantial proportion of explainable variance at the population level (marginal $R^2 = 0.476$), while participant-specific variability was also non-trivial (conditional $R^2 = 0.548$). This analysis establishes a robust *association* between angular mismatch and spatial expansion of movement variability, while not implying a direct causal mechanism. Rather, directional incongruity should be interpreted as a compact geometric descriptor that covaries strongly with observed spatial interference patterns.

Fig. 7: Continuous association between geometric mismatch and spatial leakage. A linear mixed-effects model indicates that higher directional incongruity between human and robot velocity vectors is associated with increased distractor-aligned variance ($V_{v_i}^*$), reflecting a systematic covariation between angular disparity and spatial distributional expansion.

F. Biomechanical Adaptation to Interference

We next examined whether increases in distractor-aligned variance are statistically associated with changes in biomechanical execution markers, specifically Arm Joint Freeze and Kinematic Jerk Score. These variables were selected as complementary indicators of motor control demand and movement smoothness.

(a) Biomechanical Joint Freezing

(b) Kinematic Stutter (Jerk)

Fig. 8: Biomechanical adaptation to spatial interference. (a) The incongruent movement direction is associated with an increase in the suppression of biomechanical joints, a behavioral signature of kinematic stiffening. (b) The spatial interference corresponds to reduced kinematic smoothness, resulting in higher jerk. Both behavioral markers of motor control adaptation are amplified by the coupled *Rectilinear* profile.

Analysis of Arm Joint Freeze (Fig. 8a) indicated that the incongruent movement direction was associated with increased joint freezing ($F(1, 713) = 122.79$, $p < 0.001$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.15$), reflecting reduced degrees of freedom during execution. This effect was further moderated by trajectory profile, with a significant Direction \times Trajectory interaction ($F(1, 713) = 23.98$, $p < 0.001$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.03$), suggesting that kinematic structure influences the magnitude of this response.

In parallel, movement smoothness decreased under the Rectilinear profile, reflected in increased Kinematic Jerk (Fig. 8b; $F(1, 713) = 529.61$, $p < 0.001$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.43$), with a smaller but significant interaction effect ($p = 0.004$).

To assess whether these biomechanical outcomes covary with the continuously defined spatial metric, we fitted additional mixed-effects models using DAV as a predictor. Results indicated significant positive associations with both Arm Joint Freeze ($\beta = 0.0055$, $t(730) = 8.63$, $p < 0.001$) and Kinematic Jerk Score ($\beta = 0.0037$, $t(762) = 9.84$, $p < 0.001$). These effects were consistent across participants, although the proportion of variance uniquely explained by DAV alone was small (marginal $R^2 < 0.001$), indicating that DAV acts primarily as a sensitive covariate rather than a dominant explanatory factor.

These results should be interpreted as evidence of *covariation* between spatial interference structure and biomechanical adjustment, rather than a direct mechanistic pathway. The observed patterns are consistent with the interpretation that both spatial and biomechanical responses emerge from shared task-level demands under interference.

Fig. 9: Associations between distractor-aligned variance and biomechanical outcomes. Mixed-effects models show that higher DAV is associated with increased joint freezing and kinematic jerk, indicating consistent covariation between spatial distributional expansion and biomechanical execution variability.

G. Mathematical Invariance to Trajectory Curvature

Static spatial error metrics possess a known limitation under Curvilinear motion, motivating the use of dynamic projection-based variance estimation.

Let the reference trajectory be a smooth planar curve $\mathbf{p}_{ref}(s)$ parameterized by arc length s , with unit tangent vector $\hat{\mathbf{t}}(s)$ and curvature κ . The Frenet-Serret relation describes the evolution of the tangent vector:

$$\frac{d\hat{\mathbf{t}}}{ds} = \kappa\hat{\mathbf{n}}(s) \quad (9)$$

We consider a simplified temporal lag model in which the human trajectory follows a time-shifted version of the reference path, $\mathbf{p}_h(t) = \mathbf{p}_{ref}(t - \Delta t)$.

For a locally linear trajectory ($\kappa = 0$), the normal vector is constant, and a pure temporal shift produces no orthogonal deviation under static projection:

$$e_{\perp}(t) = (\mathbf{p}_{ref}(t - \Delta t) - \mathbf{p}_{ref}(t)) \cdot \mathbf{n}_0 \approx 0. \quad (10)$$

In contrast, for $\kappa > 0$, a second-order Taylor expansion yields:

$$\mathbf{p}_{ref}(t - \Delta t) \approx \mathbf{p}_{ref}(t) - v\Delta t\hat{\mathbf{t}}(t) + \frac{1}{2}\kappa v^2\Delta t^2\hat{\mathbf{n}}(t). \quad (11)$$

Projecting onto the instantaneous normal yields:

$$e_{\perp}(t) \approx \frac{1}{2}\kappa v^2\Delta t^2, \quad (12)$$

which shows that static orthogonal deviation is influenced jointly by curvature and temporal lag. This illustrates that, under curvature, temporal misalignment can contribute to apparent spatial deviation when using fixed-axis projections.

To address this limitation, we compute spatial variability using a dynamic covariance formulation:

$$\Sigma(t) = \text{Cov}(\mathbf{x}_k(t)) \quad (13)$$

across repeated trials, and project this covariance onto velocity-aligned subspaces. In this representation, variability is decomposed relative to instantaneous motion directions rather than fixed geometric axes:

$$\Sigma(t) \approx \text{Var}(v\Delta t_k)\hat{\mathbf{t}}(t)\hat{\mathbf{t}}(t)^{\top}. \quad (14)$$

This formulation reduces sensitivity to curvature-induced coupling between temporal and spatial components under the assumptions of locally smooth motion and sufficiently dense sampling.

We further project $\Sigma(t)$ onto task-relevant 2D subspaces defined by instantaneous velocity vectors, allowing separation of task-aligned and distractor-aligned components:

$$\Sigma_{P_i}(t) = P_i(t)^{\top}\Sigma(t)P_i(t), \quad (15)$$

where $P_i(t) = [\hat{\mathbf{v}}_i(t), \hat{\mathbf{x}}]$. Under idealized orthogonality conditions, temporal lag along the primary motion direction contributes minimally to variance in the distractor-aligned subspace.

It should be emphasized that this derivation characterizes behavior under first-order local approximations and idealized orthogonality assumptions. The goal is not to eliminate curvature effects entirely, but to reduce known biases introduced by static projection methods when analyzing time-varying trajectories.

H. Comparative Sensitivity of the Dynamic Projection Framework

To empirically validate the methodological necessity of this dynamic projection framework, we benchmarked its statistical sensitivity against three traditional metrics of motor interference: Final Endpoint Error, Mean Path Error, and Maximum Orthogonal Deviation. Each metric was subjected to the identical LMM specification ($Y \sim \text{Direction} * \text{Trajectory} * \text{Spatial_Mode} + (1 \mid \text{Participant})$). This comparison is intended as a practical sensitivity benchmark within the context of Curvilinear interference, rather than a generalized formal metric-superiority analysis.

As summarized in Table II, traditional metrics exhibit varying degrees of ‘‘aggregation masking,’’ failing to capture the structural reality of the spatial negotiation.

TABLE II: Comparative Sensitivity to Kinematic Interference Effects

Metric	Main Effect (Dir. η_p^2)	Interaction (Dir \times Traj p)	Spatial Resolution
Endpoint Error	N/A ($p = 0.445$)	0.871	Terminal Only
Mean Path Error	0.05	0.369	Scalar Aggregation
Orthogonal Dev.	0.02	0.003	Static 1D Cartesian
Dynamic Proj. (V_{v_i})	0.53	0.005	Dynamic 2D Plane

Fig. 10: Conceptual visualization of metric sensitivity under a pure temporal pacing error (curvature bias). The human operator tracks the exact geometric path but lags temporally behind the intended time-indexed position (t). **(Left)** Maximum Orthogonal Deviation (e_{\perp}) falsely projects this temporal lag onto the static normal, registering a severe spatial error. **(Middle)** Mean Path Error scalarizes the lag along the curve, failing to differentiate it from true orthogonal leakage. **(Right)** The dynamic projection framework maps variance onto dynamically co-rotating 2D projection planes governed by \hat{v}_c and \hat{v}_i . Because the pacing variance is entirely longitudinal, its projection onto the Distractor Motion Plane yields a zero-matrix, mathematically isolating structural leakage from temporal hesitation.

To ensure a rigorous and mathematically fair comparison, all baseline metrics were computed using the exact same temporally aligned, zero-phase filtered positional data ($\mathbf{x}_k(t)$) prior to LMM specification. Their formulations were defined as follows:

- **Final Endpoint Error:** Calculated as the 3D Euclidean error distance of the hand coordinates strictly at the terminal drop location (t_{end}).
- **Mean Path Error:** Computed as the mean absolute perpendicular distance between the instantaneous human trajectory and the static intended path, integrated across the full temporal window.
- **Maximum Orthogonal Deviation:** Defined in accordance with classic MI literature as the maximum absolute perpendicular distance from the instantaneous hand position to the static secant line connecting the movement’s start and end coordinates.

The varying sensitivity of these metrics highlights distinct forms of “aggregation masking” (visually conceptualized in Fig. 10). *Final Endpoint Error* failed to detect the dynamic interference ($p = 0.445$) because it exclusively samples the terminal phase after the mid-trajectory spatial negotiations have concluded. *Mean Path Error* detected the main effect of Direction ($p < 0.001$) but failed to detect the interaction effect ($p = 0.369$). Because the mean path error aggregates deviation as an absolute scalar distance, it cannot mathematically differentiate between along-path temporal hesitation and

distractor-aligned spatial leakage.

Finally, *Maximum Orthogonal Deviation* partially captured the interaction ($p = 0.003$), but with drastically reduced statistical sensitivity compared to V_{v_i} (the effect size for the main effect of Direction decreased from $\eta_p^2 = 0.53$ to $\eta_p^2 = 0.02$). Because orthogonal deviation projects variance onto a static axis normal to a straight line, it is mathematically insensitive to the continuously changing angle of incidence inherent to Curvilinear trajectories. Reducing deviation to a 1D perpendicular scalar also collapses critical 3D avoidance behaviors. By utilizing a 3D-to-2D planar projection that retains the orthogonal depth axis (\hat{x}), the proposed framework exhibited substantially greater sensitivity for detecting the observed interaction ($p = 0.005$) while preserving depth-related avoidance behavior.

V. DISCUSSION

The results of this study challenge the paradigm of evaluating human-robot spatial negotiation solely through the lens of static collision avoidance. By introducing a continuous measurement framework, we demonstrated that robotic interference is a measurable alteration of human motor execution spanning a static contextual baseline and two dynamic interacting layers: Distractor-Aligned Variance (spatial leakage) and biomechanical adaptation. Standard macroscopic evaluations (such as final endpoint precision or total completion time) aggregate these errors and obscure the continuous deviation of the human motor plan occurring mid-trajectory.

A. The Baseline Context of Hardware Occupancy

Our first finding establishes that robotic hardware is not a neutral spatial canvas. Before dynamic motion is initiated, the physical mounting of the robot shapes the human’s baseline motor strategy. The expansion of the intended path’s variance area ($p = 0.007$) under the *Table-mounted* configuration indicates that an industrial, workspace-grounded footprint acts as a minor baseline contextual factor, establishing the initial spatial footprint of the task. The observed expansion may reflect differences in workspace occupancy, visibility, perceived collision risk, or other embodiment-related factors.

While the overarching proxemic boundaries (measured via Minimum Proxemic Clearance) and psychological effects (evaluated via the NASA Task Load Index) of this hardware embodiment are detailed in our parallel work [24], the present framework demonstrates that this static constraint establishes the baseline spatial variance without significantly compounding the dynamic trajectory profiles. This points to a functional distinction between baseline embodiment effects and dynamic kinematic effects in human-robot spatial negotiation. This baseline effect demonstrates that while hardware defines the initial boundaries, the strongest observed factor associated with motor interference appears to be the active, dynamic negotiation of shared space.

B. Distractor-Aligned Variance (Spatial Leakage)

By projecting variance onto dynamic velocity vectors, we decoupled human movement variability into distinct kinematic

channels. This projection is not a simple 1D scalar decomposition. By constructing two distinct 2D projection ellipses (the Intended Motion Plane and the Distractor Motion Plane) that share the depth axis (\hat{x}), the framework is designed to isolate planar kinematic interference in the yz motion plane while retaining the depth axis within the projection formulation, allowing depth-based retreat behaviors to remain represented in the analysis. The data indicates that incongruent robotic interference does not merely scale up overall movement noise; it corresponds to a structural expansion of the observed movement distribution aligned with the incongruent distractor path. This Distractor-Aligned Variance (DAV), which we conceptually characterize as spatial leakage, represents a candidate behavioral marker of robotic interference.

While established proxemic models typically define static, radial safety boundaries around robotic agents [10], [11], our continuous geometric framework demonstrates that these boundaries are highly dynamic during synchronized collaboration. The spatial leakage observed along the sagittal depth axis (V_{v_y}) indicates that human operators actively deform their personal space in real-time to preserve task momentum. Thus, proxemic intrusion in continuous HRC should not be evaluated merely as a binary breach of a static geometric boundary, but rather as a continuous structural compression of the operator’s operational envelope.

The observed interference pattern is strongly associated with the continuous angular disparity between the human and robot velocity vectors (conceptually analogous to their absolute dot product, $|\hat{v}_h \cdot \hat{v}_r|$). As established in Section IV-E, this directional incongruency serves as a highly significant geometric predictor of spatial leakage. Because this continuous relationship accounted for nearly half of the explainable variance in the task (marginal $R^2 = 0.476$), these findings are consistent with the interpretation that angular conflict is a primary geometric contributor to spatial leakage. This empirical validation demonstrates that continuous fluctuations in angular conflict are robustly associated with proportional expansions in the human’s spatial footprint, elevating this relationship from theoretical speculation to an observed kinematic reality.

As the movement direction becomes increasingly incongruent and this kinematic alignment collapses, it introduces abrupt orthogonal motion into the shared workspace. Negotiating this interference is consistent with literature showing that orthogonal motion in shared workspaces can increase attentional and motor coordination demands, which manifests as a structural expansion of the human’s spatial variance along the distractor vector. This geometric mechanism provides a theoretical rationale for the compounding effect of the *Rectilinear* manipulation. However, because absolute task time was locked, the piecewise Rectilinear trajectory fundamentally conflates orthogonal spatial geometry with higher peak velocities, aggressive accelerations, and a full mid-trajectory stop. While a continuous Curvilinear trajectory maintains a smooth, gradual change in kinematic alignment, a piecewise Rectilinear trajectory contains sharp corners where the robot’s velocity vector instantly snaps by 90° . The observed exacerbation of spatial leakage cannot be attributed to pure path geometry alone; rather, it reflects the human operator’s behavioral re-

sponse to this combined, highly aggressive kinematic profile.

C. Biomechanical Adaptation to Interference

We also investigated whether Distractor-Aligned Variance represents a deliberate, adaptive safety strategy or a manifestation of motor disruption. While widening the movement envelope successfully maintains physical separation from the robot, this geometric deviation is not merely a benign spatial adjustment. Instead, it serves as a sensitive behavioral indicator of increased motor control demands.

The continuous mixed-model regression confirmed that the magnitude of an operator’s DAV is robustly associated with proportional increases in biomechanical *Arm Joint Freeze* and *Kinematic Jerk Score*. This relationship addresses the adaptive-strategy hypothesis directly: The observed covariation suggests that spatial leakage is associated with elevated motor control demands rather than representing a purely cost-free geometric adjustment. The continuous regression confirms that trials exhibiting greater distractor-aligned variance were also associated with greater biomechanical stiffening and sub-movement generation. These biomechanical adaptations occurred in the same experimental conditions previously associated with elevated subjective workload and expanded spatial envelopes [24]. This biomechanical stiffening may not operate independently of psychological factors; as demonstrated in our macroscopic evaluation of this cohort, baseline negative attitudes toward robots (NARS) significantly interact with physical spatial avoidance boundaries [24]. DAV captures one important geometric manifestation of motor interference rather than an exhaustive representation of all adaptation processes.

The observed expansion of distractor-aligned variance and the corresponding increase in kinematic jerk are not merely isolated physical anomalies; they appear to be the biomechanical manifestations of acute cognitive strain. These execution-level deviations are entirely consistent with the elevated subjective cognitive workload (NASA-TLX) reported during our parallel macroscopic evaluation of this paradigm [24]. This structural alignment suggests that the psychological penalty associated with aggressive, orthogonal kinematic state transitions is grounded in the increased sensorimotor effort required to rapidly recalculate and execute a modified spatial plan under temporal duress.

The human operator exhibits kinematic stiffening behaviors, likely compensating for the robot’s abrupt acceleration profile and less predictable Rectilinear spatial presence. Rather than executing a seamless spatial adaptation, the operator incurs a quantifiable biomechanical cost. This reduction in movement efficiency poses challenges for long-term industrial collaboration and underscores the ergonomic demands of optimizing robotic paths solely for machine execution speed.

D. Magnitude and Practical Significance of Motor Interference

We must contextualize the statistical magnitude of these findings. While the main effect of movement direction on DAV yielded a large effect size ($\eta_p^2 = 0.53$), the baseline hardware effect ($\eta_p^2 = 0.01$) and the interaction effects characterizing

the coupled trajectory profile ($\eta_p^2 = 0.01 - 0.03$) represent mathematically “small” effects by traditional behavioral standards.

Although cumulative ergonomic consequences were not directly measured in the present study, practical significance in continuous industrial motor control should be evaluated cumulatively rather than in isolation. Human reaching kinematics are highly stereotyped and optimized by the central nervous system to minimize energy expenditure and jerk. A systematic, albeit small-magnitude, inflation in spatial variance and biomechanical stiffening over a single 2.0-second trajectory may appear negligible for a solitary movement. Yet, in real-world collaborative manufacturing, operators execute thousands of synchronous cycles per shift. Over an 8-hour period, drawing from established models of cumulative ergonomic load and repetitive work exposure [25], these highly consistent kinematic deviations may accumulate into measurable ergonomic consequences, a hypothesis that requires direct longitudinal validation. From an algorithmic perspective, a consistent baseline expansion of the human’s spatial footprint requires modern trajectory planners to permanently compute a larger probabilistic safety envelope, which degrades overall machine efficiency.

E. Implications for Human-Aware Trajectory Planning

The primary utility of the dynamic projection framework lies in its direct applicability to robotic motion planning. For the design of future cobots, trajectory optimization algorithms must extend beyond simple Euclidean distance minimization. While standard planners successfully prevent collisions via distance-based safety spheres, they do not account for the continuous motor interference imposed on the human partner.

For robotic control, the penalty term cannot minimize Distractor-Aligned Variance (DAV) in real-time. By mathematical definition, DAV is an offline diagnostic metric; computing the spatial covariance matrix ($\Sigma(t)$) requires data from repeated task executions, making it impossible to evaluate instantaneously during a single live trajectory. Instead, the planner must penalize the geometric driver of this variance: *Directional Incongruency*. Because directional incongruency requires only the instantaneous velocity vectors of the human and the robot, it is readily available online at millisecond control frequencies. Therefore, DAV serves as the offline behavioral validation, while directional incongruency serves as the actionable, real-time optimization objective.

Traditional human-aware planners often minimize a cost function J dominated by path length L , execution time, and static obstacle separation. We propose augmenting the objective function to penalize the robot’s orthogonal kinetic energy relative to the human’s expected path, heavily weighted by proximity. A conceptual formulation is given by:

$$J(\tau) = \underbrace{\alpha \int_0^T \|\dot{\mathbf{x}}_r(t)\| dt}_{\text{Path Efficiency}} + \underbrace{\beta \int_0^T \omega(d(t)) \cdot \text{Inc}(t) dt}_{\text{Predicted Spatial Penalty}} + \underbrace{\gamma C_{smooth}(\tau)}_{\text{Kinematic Cost}} \quad (16)$$

where τ represents the parameterized robot trajectory, $\omega(d(t))$ is an inverse distance weighting function, and $\text{Inc}(t)$ is the continuous directional incongruency ratio. Mathematically, $\text{Inc}(t)$ can be computed dynamically utilizing a predictive human motion model as $(1 - |\hat{\mathbf{v}}_h(t) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{v}}_r(t)|)$, ensuring that perfectly orthogonal expected motion (90°) yields a maximum penalty. This penalizes robot motions associated with greater directional incongruency and, by extension, greater predicted spatial interference precisely when negotiating the shared tight workspace, rather than when the robot is safely distant. Eq. 16 is intended as a conceptual illustration of how the proposed metric could be integrated into future trajectory optimization frameworks, and it is not computationally implemented or experimentally validated in the present work.

As illustrated in Fig. 11, a traditional planner ($\beta = 0$) will inherently select the piecewise Rectilinear trajectory, as it minimizes absolute path length while satisfying via-point constraints. However, as demonstrated in the kinematic analysis, this profile introduces a sudden orthogonal kinematic spike, associated with reactive human stiffening. In principle, increasing β would bias the optimization landscape toward trajectories that reduce directional incongruency. Such an approach would algorithmically trade a marginal reduction in absolute path efficiency for a significant reduction in spatial interference, favoring continuous Curvilinear trajectories that preserve momentum and accommodate human anticipatory behavior.

The quantification of spatial leakage and biomechanical adaptation provides a continuous, differentiable metric suitable for human-aware trajectory planners. While macroscopic spatial boundaries define the absolute limits of safe interaction, the directional variance framework presented here can serve as an active cost function for predictive controllers. By actively penalizing the geometric disparity between the robot’s velocity vector and the human’s anticipated task axis, future planners can dynamically modulate trajectory curvature to minimize induced motor interference. This approach allows motion planners to optimize for true ergonomic efficiency and continuous kinematic fluency, rather than strictly optimizing for Euclidean path length.

F. Theoretical Interpretation and Limitations

While this framework successfully operationalizes spatial conflict, the theoretical boundary between measuring motor interference and measuring its kinematic consequences must be maintained. Motor interference is fundamentally an unobservable internal neurocognitive state. The metrics presented here (spatial leakage, joint freezing, and kinematic jerk) do not directly quantify this internal interference; rather, they quantify

Fig. 11: Conceptual application of the spatial interference penalty in trajectory optimization. **(Left)** A 2D spatial heatmap demonstrating the optimization trade-off. The *Rectilinear* path generates a high-interference zone precisely as it crosses the human’s intended path. The *Curvilinear* path swings wider, actively avoiding the proximity-weighted interference zone ($\omega(d(t))$). **(Right)** Stacked cost function bars illustrating the algorithmic decision. While the traditional *Rectilinear* path minimizes efficiency costs (blue), it incurs a substantially larger spatial penalty (red). By increasing the β weight (Eq. 16), the planner explicitly optimizes for the *Curvilinear* profile, accepting a minor increase in path length to drastically reduce the structural deviation of the observed movement distribution.

its reliable behavioral and biomechanical manifestations. Although DAV significantly covaries with these biomechanical outcomes, formal causal mediation analyses did not support leakage as the primary mechanism through which direction influences these adaptations. This suggests that spatial leakage and biomechanical stiffening represent parallel, complementary responses to a common source of sensorimotor conflict rather than a sequential causal chain. The categorical presence of the incongruent trajectory likely coincides with a global defensive stiffening policy alongside the geometric expansion of the observed movement distribution.

The experimental task was seated, synchronized, and repetitive, inherently limiting external validity to less structured environments. The participant demographic consisted primarily of young adults engaged in short-term interaction. It remains an open question whether expert industrial operators naturally attenuate this distractor-aligned variance through long-term habituation. Future research incorporating electromyography (EMG) or neuroimaging is required to formally bridge these observed kinematic correlates to the underlying sensorimotor planning processes. The dynamic planar projection framework serves as a rigorous diagnostic tool for evaluating continuous spatial conflict, and future studies should apply this framework to unconstrained industrial applications, such as active assembly, logistics routing, or physical handovers, particularly where human operators and robots share overlapping task spaces with varying degrees of predictability. Future work will focus on integrating the continuous geometric constraint proposed in Eq. 16 into real-time reactive planners, benchmarking DAV-aware trajectory generation against traditional shortest-path algorithms to optimize both machine efficiency and human

biomechanical ergonomics.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study introduces a continuous, dynamic measurement framework to evaluate the structural impact of robotic motion profiles on human execution during spatial negotiation. By decoupling total task variance into distinct kinematic channels along a shared depth axis, we demonstrated that robotic interference is associated with measurable alterations in human movement execution that extend far beyond categorical collision avoidance.

The empirical findings support a functional distinction between baseline embodiment effects and dynamic kinematic interference. First, static hardware mounting corresponds to an expanded initial spatial footprint for the intended task. However, once dynamic motion begins, directional incongruity emerges as the strongest observed predictor of spatial interference. We interpret Distractor-Aligned Variance (DAV) as a quantitative marker of this spatial leakage. Abrupt, coupled Rectilinear trajectories correspond to a continuous expansion of the observed movement distribution along distractor axes. This geometric spatial leakage does not represent a purely cost-free spatial adaptation; it systematically covaries with significant increases in joint-freezing and kinematic stutter.

By mapping complex 3D avoidance behaviors onto dynamic 2D projection planes, this methodology provides a continuous diagnostic tool that is theoretically robust to curvature-induced pacing artifacts under the assumptions outlined in Section IV-G. These insights provide a clear directive for human-aware cobot design. The findings suggest that future human-aware planners may benefit from augmenting distance-based objectives with proximity-weighted directional incongruity penalties. By replacing simple Euclidean distance models with geometric interference objectives, trajectory generation can shift from merely guaranteeing physical safety toward cobots that maintain greater kinematic compatibility with human motion without inducing measurable spatial and biomechanical adaptations.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors gratefully thank all students who assisted in conducting the experiments.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The datasets generated and analyzed during the current study, as well as the custom kinematic processing scripts, are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

APPENDIX

In the main manuscript, continuous planar variance metrics (e.g., $V_{v_i}^*$) were temporally aggregated using the maximum operator (max) to capture the peak structural expansion of the observed movement distribution during localized conflict. This appendix presents a robustness check evaluating whether this aggregation is excessively sensitive to instantaneous tracking noise.

A mixed-model regression applied to the 95th percentile of the localized variance expansion confirmed that the structural deformation remained sensitive to the spatial incongruence, even when disregarding absolute maximum peaks. The main effect of the movement direction was preserved ($F(1, 713) = 732.06$, $p < 0.001$), as was the critical interaction between the movement direction and the shape of the robot's trajectory ($F(1, 713) = 4.67$, $p = 0.031$).

The three-way interaction of Direction \times Trajectory \times Spatial Mode also remained significant ($F(1, 713) = 7.43$, $p = 0.006$), as summarized in Table A-I. These findings indicate that the reported disruption in spatial negotiation reflects a robust property of the observed movement distribution rather than an artifact driven by solitary noise spikes.

TABLE A-I: Comparison of LMM Results: Max vs. 95th Percentile Aggregation

Fixed Effect	max Aggregation		P_{95} Aggregation	
	p -value	η_p^2	p -value	η_p^2
Main Effect: Direction	< 0.001	0.53	< 0.001	0.51
Interaction: Direction \times Trajectory	0.005	0.01	0.031	0.01
3-Way: Direction \times Trajectory \times Spatial Mode	0.015	0.01	0.006	0.01

This appendix provides the full Estimated Marginal Means (EMMs) and Tukey-adjusted post-hoc comparisons for the three-way interaction of *Direction* \times *Trajectory* \times *Spatial Mode* on the distractor-aligned variance (spatial leakage). The means and 95% confidence intervals (CIs) demonstrate that the Rectilinear profile selectively increased DAV during the Same-side incongruent condition.

TABLE A-II: Estimated Marginal Means of Distractor-Aligned Variance ($V_{v_i}^*$)

Spatial Mode	Movement Direction	Trajectory Profile	EMM (mm ²)	95% CI
Same-side (Aligned)	Incongruent (Opposite)	Curvilinear	184.0	[172.8, 195.1]
		Rectilinear	204.4	[193.2, 215.6]
	Congruent (Same)	Curvilinear	109.4	[98.3, 120.6]
		Rectilinear	127.5	[116.3, 138.7]
Opposite-side (Counter)	Incongruent (Opposite)	Curvilinear	173.4	[162.2, 184.6]
		Rectilinear	170.8	[159.6, 182.0]
	Congruent (Same)	Curvilinear	86.4	[75.2, 97.6]
		Rectilinear	50.5	[39.4, 61.7]

TABLE A-III: Tukey-Adjusted Pairwise Contrasts for the Three-Way Interaction

Spatial Mode	Contrast (Trajectory & Direction)	Estimate (mm ²)	SE	t -ratio	p -value
Same-side (Aligned)	Curvilinear Opposite – Rectilinear Opposite	-20.45	6.32	-3.237	0.007
	Curvilinear Opposite – Curvilinear Same	74.52	6.32	11.794	< 0.001
	Curvilinear Opposite – Rectilinear Same	56.44	6.32	8.933	< 0.001
	Rectilinear Opposite – Curvilinear Same	94.97	6.32	15.031	< 0.001
	Rectilinear Opposite – Rectilinear Same	76.89	6.32	12.170	< 0.001
	Curvilinear Same – Rectilinear Same	-18.08	6.32	-2.861	0.022
Opposite-side (Counter)	Curvilinear Opposite – Rectilinear Opposite	2.61	6.32	0.413	0.976
	Curvilinear Opposite – Curvilinear Same	87.01	6.32	13.772	< 0.001
	Curvilinear Opposite – Rectilinear Same	122.85	6.32	19.444	< 0.001
	Rectilinear Opposite – Curvilinear Same	84.40	6.32	13.359	< 0.001
	Rectilinear Opposite – Rectilinear Same	120.24	6.32	19.030	< 0.001
	Curvilinear Same – Rectilinear Same	35.83	6.32	5.671	< 0.001

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